

Detection of Antibiotic-Producing Fungi from the Soil Environment of Zamfara State and the GC-MS Analysis of Crude Fungal Extracts

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Abstract

Antibiotics produced by soil microorganisms, are crucial for treating bacterial and fungal diseases. Due to antibiotic resistance, a broad spectrum of antibiotics from fungi is needed. Soil samples from Zamfara state were used for detecting and analyzing fungal extracts. The soil's physico-chemical study involved parameters like temperature, pH, moisture content, electrical conductivity, texture, and color. Isolates were isolated using pour plate methods, identified using lecto-phenolcotton blue staining, and characterized using 18S rRNA. Antimicrobial compounds were extracted using solvent extraction and thin layer chromatography. The data was analyzed using mean, standard error of mean, and One-Way-ANOVA. The samples had varying colors and textures, with sample C having the highest mean pH of 7.42. The highest temperature was 26^oC for samples B, H, and J, while the highest electrical value was 105 for sample D. Six fungi were isolated from the soil samples and these include; *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Cladosporium herbarum*, and *Epicoccum nigrum*. The fungi isolated were tested against some test pathogens viz: *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* to determine their sensitivity and resistance pattern using agar well diffusion method. All the organisms inhibited at least one pathogen, *Epicoccum nigrum* was found to have the highest activity against *C. albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* with inhibition zones of 12mm and 10mm, followed by *Rhizoctonia solani* with inhibition zones of 12mm and 8mm respectively. While *Aspergillus fumigatus* had zones of inhibition of 10mm against both *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* respectively. *Cladosporium herbarum* had the least zone of inhibition (8mm) against the test organisms. Consequently, the GC-MS analysis displayed bioactive compounds, namely, Phytol, Diethyl phthalate, Pentafluoropropionate, 2-octanol, Methanamine and Propylamine. The study reveals the potentials of fungi isolated from the soil environment of Zamfara state to produce antifungal compounds, highlighting the need for further exploration and the use of fractionation and NMR techniques for their isolation and purification.

Keywords: 2-octanol, Antibiotic producing fungi, Diethyl phthalate, GC-MS, Methanamine, Pentafluoropropionate, Phytol

1.0 Introduction

The complex nature of soils make them reservoirs for a wide variety of soil microbes that produce antibiotics; according to [1], around 60% of the nearly 500 antibiotics that are found each year come from the soil.

According to [2], soil is the hot spot for easily retrieving antibiotic-producing microbes and is a very heterogeneous habitat rich in diverse

microorganisms. Moreover, soils that pose challenges to the micro-biota exhibit high variation in biotic and abiotic conditions, forcing soil microbes to adapt by developing strategies such as the production of antimicrobials for survival [3]. Antibiotic-producing microorganisms have thus mostly come from soil [4].

Most modern antibiotics are found through systematic searching, despite the fact that the first commercially produced antibiotic, penicillin, was discovered by accident. Since the soil is a vast

repository of microorganisms, many of which go undiscovered, it is a potential source of many species with the ability to produce new antibiotics, and when new antibiotic producers are being sought, attention is most frequently turned to the soil microbes [5].

Globally, the incidence of antibiotic resistance in important microbial pathogens is rising at a startling rate [6]. At least some bacterial infections may become resistant to the current antimicrobial agents due to the growing global problem of antibiotic resistance, which calls for the development of new antimicrobials and a more sensible approach to the use of antibiotics [7].

In developing nations like Nigeria, where soil is abundant, research on fungi that produce antibiotics from Zamfara State's soil environment is lacking. Thus, the goal of this study was to identify possible antibiotic-producing fungi from Zamfara State's soil. The objectives of this research were to screen soil of Zamfara state for antibiotic producing fungi, produce antibiotics from the isolated antibiotic producing fungi, use their crude extracts against pathogenic *Candida albicans* and Gram positive *Staphylococcus aureus*. Carryout both molecular characterization of the potent fungal isolates and GC-MS analysis of the N-hexane extracts of the identified isolates.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample Site

Soil samples were collected in Kotorkoshi and neighboring towns. Kotorkoshi has an undisturbed natural and mountainous environment. Soils from such location are potential sources of antibiotic producing microbes [8]. High levels of competition and the synthesis of extra cellular products among microorganisms in such environment result from the pressures caused by the abundance of microorganisms in these environments. As a result, undisturbed natural environments have been identified as an important source of biotechnologically significant microorganisms, including antibiotic producers, and there is a high chance of detecting novel antibiotic producers in such an environment [8]. Kotorkoshi is under Bungudu local government area, it is located in the eastern part of Zamfara State between the latitude of 11°48'33.73"N and longitude of 8°50'39.19"E and at the elevation of 375 meters above sea

level. Kotorkoshi has a population of about 183,162 [9]. The area has an average rainfall of about 800-900mm and annual temperature range between 25-34°C. The major occupation of Kotorkoshi is farming.

2.2 Sample Collection

A top soil sample to a depth of at least four inches was obtained using two different sampling procedures in each sampling point, by systemic random sampling using zigzag pattern. The samples were properly labeled with date, type of soil, including location, and were immediately transported to Microbiology laboratory, Federal University Gusau, for determination of physicochemical parameters and isolation of antibiotic-producing fungi, respectively.

2.3 Determination of Physicochemical Parameters of soil

The method described by [10] was used in determining the color, texture, pH, electrical conductivity, particle density and moisture. The average mean of the three (3) consecutive readings was then taken.

2.4 Sample preparation

Sterile test tubes were taken, marked, and labeled for each soil sample. Nine (9) ml of distilled water was poured into the test tubes. A soil suspension was made by adding 1g of the soil sample to the 9ml of distilled water in the test tubes for each soil sample, and was vortexed. One (1) ml of this solution was taken and transferred to the second test tube and vortexed and from second to third. Hence each soil sample was serially diluted. Serial dilution technique was employed to reduce the microbial load, obtain discrete and purify colonies with varying morphologies on their various substrates.

2.5 Test Organisms

Two test organisms *Candida albicans* and *Escherichia coli* were collected from stock culture in Microbiology laboratory of Federal University, Gusau. They were prepared with a density equivalent to 0.5Mc Farland turbidity standards.

2.6 Culturing and identification of fungi from the soil sample

A 10-fold serial dilution of the soil sample was done. Aliquots of 0.1ml from the selected dilutions were inoculated on SDA plates in duplicates followed by incubation at 28°C for 3-5 days. The resulting colonies in potato dextrose agar plates were further inoculated on fresh potato dextrose agar plates followed by incubation at 28°C for 3 to 5 days. Each discrete colony from the pure culture was stored in an agar slant for further analysis and identification.

2.7 Macroscopic and Microscopic Examination of Fungal Isolates

Microscopic examination of each fungal isolate was done by picking fungal mycelia with the help of a sterilized needle and placing it on a glass slide containing a drop of lacto-phenol cotton blue stain, and was covered with a cover slip and viewed under microscope using 40x and 100x objective lens of the microscope.

The macroscopic examination of fungal isolate was carried out by comparing the fungal isolates with the pictorial atlas of soil fungi. Some morphological features such as physical appearance, color and growth pattern of each fungal colony on SDA media were observed.

2.8 Molecular identification of fungal isolates

The isolates' genomic DNA was extracted using the Zymo Research Quick-DNA (Fungal/Bacteria Miniprep kit; catalog number D6005). This was completed in compliance with the manufacturer's guidelines. A 1% (w/v) Agarose gel electrophoresis was set up to assess the extracted DNA samples' purity. The following 36 cycles of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification reactions were carried out in an Applied Biosystems GeneAmp PCR System 9700:

Initial denaturation step of 94°C for 5 minutes, denaturation step of 30 seconds at 94°C, annealing steps of 56°C for 30 seconds, 72°C for 45 seconds, and 72°C for seven minutes as the last extension step. For 40 minutes, 1.5% agarose gel containing PCR amplicons was operated at 100 volts. One kb DNA ladder from New England Biolab was the ladder that was used.

2.9 PCR Products purification

The PCR tubes were filled with 20 µl of 100% ethanol, incubated for 15 minutes at room temperature, and then spun down for an additional 15 minutes at 10,000 rpm. The supernatant was then decanted, and 15 minutes of spinning at 10,000 rpm followed. The PCR tubes were filled with 40 µl of 70% ethanol, the supernatant was decanted, and the tubes were allowed to air-dry. Ten microliters of ultrapure water were added to each PCR tube following air drying. Amplicon's presence was verified on a 1.5% agarose gel.

2.10 Sequencing

From the amplified products, the amplicons with a single band were chosen, and they were purified according to the manufacturer's instructions (QIAquick PCR Purification Kit, cat. No. 28106). Big Dye terminator sequencing kit (Applied Biosystems) was used for the sequencing process. Ethanol EDTA solution was used to purify and precipitate the unincorporated dye terminators. Next, the pellets were again dissolved in Applied Biosystems Cat. No. 4311320 HiDi formamide buffer. This sequencing was done with a 3130xl Genetic Analyzer.

2.11 Analysis of 18S rRNA

The PCR amplification of the total genomic DNA of the isolates was performed using the method of [11]. The regions of nrDNA (ITS1 and ITS2) were amplified using the primers 5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3' and 5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3' [12]. In order to find identical matches with already defined reference sequences, the 18S rRNA sequence was examined using the Basic local alignment search tool (BLAST), which is accessible from the National Center for Biotechnology Information website (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>).

2.12 Standardization of the inoculum

McFarland standard was prepared by adding 0.5ml of 0.048mol/L BaCl₂ (1.17w/v BaCl₂^{2H₂O}) into 99.5ml of 0.18mol/l H₂SO₄ (1%W/V) with constant stirring. The equal volume of standard solution was distributed into same size screw capped test tubes. The test tubes were tightly sealed and stored at room temperature to prevent them from evaporation and light. Before use, turbidity standard was vigorously agitated by using vortex mixer to provide a consistent turbid look before comparison with the fungal

suspension[13].

2.13 Antifungal susceptibility testing

Antibacterial activities of the isolates were tested using agar well diffusion method. The inoculum's turbidity was compared with that of the standard 0.5 McFarland solution. The turbidity was adjusted, sterile cotton swab was dipped into the suspension and streaked over the entire surface of the plate medium for three times by rotating the plate approximately at 60°C to ensure uniform distribution of the inoculums [8]. The wells were prepared on potato dextrose agar (India) plate using sterile cork borer (6mm in diameter). A volume of 10µl each of fungal isolates were carefully dispensed into each well and allowed to diffuse at 30°C for 45 minutes and incubated. After incubation, zones of inhibitions around each well were measured and recorded [8].

2.14 Antifungal compounds production

Isolates showing antimicrobial activity in the preliminary screening were further tested in a small scale sub-merged fermentation state for antibiotic production. A loopful of fungal cultures were suspended in 250ML Sabroud dextrose broth. The broth cultures then put on a shaker (inside incubator machine) at 2000rpm and incubated at 28°C for 21 days [14].

2.15 Extraction of metabolite using solvent extraction method

The metabolites were extracted for gas chromatography (GC) analysis using the method used by [11] with some modifications. The extraction was performed by dispensing the broth culture of 21-day-grown fungal isolates into separate 500mL Erlenmeyer flasks. The culture filtrates were added to an equal amount of n-hexane and ethanol (1:1) and shaken vigorously for one hour. The contents of the flasks were filtered by the use of Whatman No. 1 filter paper on a separate or funnel and the aqueous phase was separated from the solvent phase, which is thought to contain an antibiotic compounds. A rotary evaporator was then used to concentrate the antibiotics in the n-hexane and Ethanol phase [8].

2.16 Thin Layer Chromatography and Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrophotometry

The analysis of Thin Layer Chromatography and Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrophotometry were carried out at Multi-user Research Laboratory Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

2.17 Separation of Extract Using TLC

Thin layer chromatography plates were manually prepared in the laboratory on a TLC plate 20cmx20cm sizes. Solvent systems were obtained which were used in the analytical TLC. Microbial crude extracts were spotted on the TLC plates using the capillary tubes. The spotted plates were then placed in the developing chamber, spotted end down; the solvents (N-hexane and ethanol) level was made below the spots, (spotted at the pencil's drawn line). The solvent then slowly rose in the adsorbent by capillary action. When the solvent front has moved to within about 1cm of the top end of the adsorbent, the TLC plates were then removed and the position of the travelled solvent front was marked. The TLC plates were then visualized under ultraviolet light 254nm and 365nm wave length [15].

2.18 Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometry Analysis (GC-MS)

This machine was employed to identify the active components of the separated compounds that showed activity in the agar overlay method. Gas chromatography mass spectrophotometer analysis was carried out on the bioactive components of the TLC fractions of each of the extract separated. GC-MS analysis was carried out for the bioactive volatile compounds with the following specification; column oven temperature 80.0°C, injection temperature 25.00°C, injection mode split, flow control mode linear velocity, pressure 108.0kpa, total flow 6.2Ml/min, column flow 1.58Ml/min, linear velocity 46.3cm/sec, purge flow 3.0mL, split ratio 1.0. Interpretation on mass spectrum GC-MS was conducted using the database of National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) having more than 62,000 patterns. The spectrum of the unknown components was compared with the spectrum of the known component stored in the NIST library. The name, molecular weight and structure of the components of the test material were ascertained.

2.19 Statistical analysis of zones of inhibition

Data was analyzed using excel spread sheet and SPSS version 23 software, while one way ANOVA and post hoc test were used to analyzed the variables.

- H_0 = the physicochemical parameters of the soil have no influence on the soil microbes.
- H_1 = the physicochemical parameters of the soil have effect on the soil microbes.

The statistical significant threshold was fixed at $P < 0.05$ (5%).

3.0 Results

Table 1: Physiochemical Properties of Soil Samples of the Different Locations in Zamfara State

Locations	Color	Texture	pH(μ s/cm)	Temperature	EC (g/cm^3)	MC (%)
Kotorkoshi	Light brown	Sandy-loamy	5.89 \pm 2	25	79.20	4.384
Furfuri	Light brown	Sandy-loamy	5.68	26	73.11	5.679
Tsafe	Dark brown	Loamy-sandy	7.42	25	101.40	2.249
Mada	Light brown	Sandy-loamy	6.95	25	105.80	4.311
Jabaka	Dark brown	Loamy-sandy	7.0	25	72.90	5.62
Bela	Dark brown	Loamy-sandy	7.46	25	89.21	2.231
Dauran	Dark brown	Loamy-sandy	6.5	25	101.0	4.311
Dosara	Light brown	Sandy-loamy	5.7	26	71.11	2.231
Danfarko	Light brown	Sandy-loamy	7.37	25	101.23	4.678
Dakitakwas	Light brown	Sandy-loamy	6.7	26	108.90	2.571

Key: pH =Hydrogen potential, EC = Electrical Conductivity, MC = Moisture Constant, Anova $P < 0.05$

3.1 Morphological identification of fungal isolates

Table 2 presents the results for the morphological identification of fungal isolates. Six fungal species were isolated

Table 1 showed results for the physicochemical parameters of soil samples. The color ranged from light brown to dark brown. The texture ranged from sandy-loamy, clay and loamy-sandy. Samples C, I, and F were found to have the highest mean pH, while sample H and B had the least mean pH. Samples B, H, and J had the highest mean temperature of 26, while, the least temperature was 25 which was recorded in sample A, C and E respectively. Mean electrical conductivities of 105.90 μ s/cm, 7.46 μ s/cm and 7.37 μ s/cm, were seen in samples J, D, and I respectively. While, sample E had the least mean electrical conductivity. Samples B and E had the highest moisture contents of 14.69% each, while the least mean moisture content was seen in sample F with a mean of 2.231%. The aforementioned alphabets (are codes) representing the names of the locations where the samples were obtained.

and identified based on morphological description, spore staining, and fungal color atlas. *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Epicoccum nigrum*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Trichoderma viride*, and *Cladosporium herbarum* were obtained.

Table 2: Morphological Identification of Fungal Isolates

S/N	Macroscopy	Inference
1.	Pale brown, hyphae, branched, septated and constricted closely near the main hyphae, conidium not formed. Varied in shapes and size.	<i>Epicoccum nigrum</i>
2.	Erect, pale brown, branched conidiophores bearing catenulate conidia in each branch blastosporous, ellipsoidal, ovate, cylindrical, and irregular in shape.	<i>Cladosporium herbarum</i>
3.	Stomata and conidia. Stromata mostly brown, globose. Lacking conidiophores. Conidiogenous cells short, hyaline or pale brown, aggregated or simple on stromata, cylindrical. Slightly constricted at septum and occasionally formed in chains.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
4.	Gray, large, uniseriate pyriform, globose small in column, smooth or spinose conidia.	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>
5.	Pale brown hyphae, branched, septated and constricted closely near the main hyphae. Conidia not formed. Monilliod cells usually formed. Sclerotia pale brown to brown, discrete or aggregated, various shapes and sizes.	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>
6.	Short, simple branched, conidiophores, bearing single conidia apically. Dark green, ellipsoidal, clavate conidia, usually 2 to 3 transversely septate, slightly curved, with conspicuous pedicels.	<i>Trichoderma viride</i>

3.2 Molecular Characterization of fungal isolates

Table 3 shows the blast Analysis of the sequences generated from the fungal isolates. The genomic DNA of the isolates were extracted and analyzed by 18S rRNA gene sequencing. For identifying microorganisms up to the species level, the 18S rRNA gene sequencing is widely used in the construction of phylogenies because of the slow rate of evolution at that gene region [16].

Six (6) suspected different fungal isolates were selected for molecular characterization.

The DNA was successfully isolated from the suspected isolates after which the extracted DNA was used for polymerase chain reaction (PCR). The success of the PCR was confirmed by agarose gel electrophoresis and all amplicons produced a band of approximately 850 bp which is expected for the amplified gene. The result of the sequence analysis of the six fungal isolates sequenced showed high quality and were identified as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Cladosporium herbarum*, *Epicoccum nigrum*, and *Rhizoctonia solani* by using web base blast tool of National Center for Biotechnology Information.

Table 3: Blast Outputs of Total Score, Percentage Identity, and Accession Number Obtained From the Isolate Sequence

Isolate code	Top hit from the NCBI Data base	Accession No.	% Identity	Total bit score
NS ₇	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	PP808486	100.00	963
NS ₈	<i>Aspergillus formigatus</i>	PP808487	88.53	538
NS ₉	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	PP808488	100.00	883
NS ₁₀	<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	PP808489	99.00	1395
NS ₁₁	<i>Cladosporium herbrum</i>	PP808490	100.00	944
NS ₁₂	<i>Epicoccum nigrum</i>	PP808491	100.00	1003

Key: NS₇=Number of sample 7, NS₈= Number of sample 8, NS₉= Number of sample 9, NS₁₀= Number of sample 10, NS₁₁= Number of sample 11, NS₁₂= Number of sample 12.

3.3 Antifungal Activity of the Isolates against Some Test Pathogens

The fungi isolated were tested against some test pathogens viz: *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* to determine their sensitivity and resistance pattern using agar

well diffusion method. The result in Table 4 shows that all the fungal isolates have antimicrobial activity against the test pathogens, which indicates that these fungi produced some antimicrobial substance (s) responsible for inhibiting the test organism. *Epicoccum nigrum* was found to have the

highest activity against *C. albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* with inhibition zones of 12mm and 10mm respectively,

Cladosporium herbarum had the least zone of inhibition (8mm) against the test organisms.

Table 4: Zones of Inhibition Shown by Different Fungal Isolates against the Test Organisms

Isolates	Zones of inhibitions {mm} of the isolates against the taste organism	
	<i>C. albicans</i> (%)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (%)
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	10	8
<i>Epicoccum nigrum</i>	12	10
<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	8	12
<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	12	8
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	10	10
<i>C. herbarum</i>	8	8

Key: C= *Cladosporium*

3.4 Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrophotometry Analysis of Fungal Extracts

Table 5 showed the result of GC-MS analysis of N-hexane extracts of fungal isolates exhibiting the presence of bioactive compounds. The presence of several compounds with known biological activity was found in the fungal extracts. The identification of bioactive chemical compounds is based on the peak area,

retention time, molecular weight and molecular formula. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of fungal isolates revealed the presence of Phytol, Diethyl phthalate, Pentafluoropropionate, 2-octanol, Methanamine, and Propylamine. The aforementioned compounds were identified as the major compounds because of their shorter RT, and they showed the highest percentage peak area and peak height [11].

Table 5: Compounds Present in Extract Produced by Fungal Isolates Analyzed by GM-MS

Isolates	Peak area %	Retention time	Compounds name	Molecular formula	Molecular structure
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	0.08	6.674	Phytol	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	
<i>Epicoccum nigrum</i>	0.88	13.28	Diethyl Phthalate	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	
<i>T. viride</i>	0.45	6.26	Pentafluoropropionate	C ₃ F ₅ O	
<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	0.03	6.274	2-octanol	C ₈ H ₁₈ O	
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	7.706	2.26	Methanamine	CH ₅ N	
<i>C. herbarum</i>	4.24	7.970	Propyl amine	C ₃ H ₉ N	

KEY: GC-MS=Gas chromatography mass spectrophotometry, T=*Trichoderma*, C=*Cladosporium*, A=*Aspergillus*

4.0 Discussion

The most important category of microorganisms on Earth are those found in soil; they produce

biological components that are active and have a wide range of uses that benefit humankind [11]. There is a noticeable variation between the soil samples in some areas of Zamfara State, according to the results of the physicochemical characteristics of the soil samples in this study region.

The organization of soil particles into aggregates is known as soil structure. These could be of different sizes, forms, and stages of expression or development [17]. The variations in pH, electrical conductivity, moisture content, porosity, and temperature observed in this study area may be attributed to the varying types and textures of soil samples.

Sample A, B, D, and H are clay-loamy, while, sample C, F and G are loamy-sandy, and the remaining three samples (I, E, and J) are sandy-loamy. The most significant property of soil is its pH level, it affects all other parameters of the soil [18]. Therefore, pH is considered while analyzing any kind of soil. If the soil, the pH range from 6-8.5 it is a normal soil and greater than 8.5 then it is said to be an alkaline soil [14].

In the present study, the pH values of the soil samples show that sample A was the most acidic with pH of 5.8, followed by sample H with a pH of 5.7. While sample B had the least acidic pH of 5.6. Sample G had a normal pH of 6.5, followed by sample J with a normal pH of 6.7, and sample D with a normal pH of 6.9. Samples E, I, C and F all had a normal soil pH of 7.0, 7.3, 7.4, and 7.4 respectively. This finding is in agreement with the study of [1]. Who reported that normal to alkaline pH are the favorite conditions for bacterial growth, and mostly in normal pH, bacterial growth has positive correlation with diversity, richness, bacterial community, and composition of soil bacteria. There are many factors that influence the soil microbial population and activity, viz; soil pH, temperature, color and texture are the most significant properties of the soil which affect soil electrical conductivities, particle density, moisture content and organic contents [18].

The temperature of the soil environments of Zamfara at the time of this study (rainy season) revealed that the soil environment of Zamfara had temperature range between 25°C and 26°C. This finding is corroborated by the report of Kekane, [18] who said soil temperature changes with season, time of the day and local condition of climate.

The effect of temperature, pH, texture, moisture

contents and electrical conductivity on soil microbes is a complex interplay of factors that can influence microbial diversity, population, growth, biomass, and activity [19].

The color of sample A in this study area ranges from light brown to dark brown. While samples I, J, A, H and D had light-brown colors, and samples C, E, F and G had dark-brown colors.

Sample J had the highest electrical conductivity of 108, followed by sample D with 105; sample G and I both had 101, while H had the least electrical conductivity of 71. The report in this study, is in agreement with the findings of [10] who reported a highest electrical conductivity of 108. The similarities observed among the two studies maybe due to the fact that the two studies were carried out during the same season (rainy season) and the same geographical location (Northwestern Nigeria).

The results of the moisture content in this study, varies from one location to another, however, it was higher in sample B (5.67%), sample E (5.62%), and sample I (4.67%). However, in sample H, F and C, the rate was about 2%. The highest moisture contents recorded in the aforementioned samples could be due to the nature of the soils (clay-loamy) in these locations. Clay soil has a good water holding capacity, as a result of its aggregates particles which confers its ability to retain water, unlike sandy soil which has a poor water holding capacity thereby less moisture content. The findings in this study are similar to the findings reported by [20] in Algeria. The similarities observed among the two studies may also be related to the same vegetational cover in these areas. Because, the roots play an important role in the exchange and maintenance of plants-animal symbiosis in the soil [21].

The cultured fungal isolates were identified based on the colony morphology and spore characteristics by referring to the manual of the pictorial atlas of soil and seed fungi. While, the microscopic examination of fungal isolates was carried out using lecto-phenol cotton blue staining.

Phylogenetic analysis and sequence alignment of the isolates revealed them as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Epicoccum nigrum*, and *Cladosporium herbarum* these have also been recovered by other researchers [22; 23; 24]. The fungi identification highlights the importance of correct identification and taxonomical

differentiation between different species of *Aspergillus* [25].

The results of the zone of Inhibition in Table 4 shows that all the fungal isolates have antimicrobial activity against two of the test pathogens (*Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus*), which indicates that these fungal isolates produce some form of antimicrobial substance(s) which are responsible for inhibiting the test organisms. *Aspergillus niger* was found to inhibit *C. albicans*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* within inhibition zones of 10mm, and 8mm. *Aspergillus fumigatus* inhibited all the test pathogens with zones of inhibition of 10mm against both *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Inhibition zones of 12mm and 10mm were respectively produced against *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by *Epicoccum nigrum*. Similarly, *Trichoderma viride* was also found to inhibit *C. albicans* (8mm), and *Staphylococcus aureus* (12mm). *C. albicans*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* were inhibited by *Rhizoctonia solani*, by producing clear zones of inhibition of 12mm, and 8mm, respectively. A similar Inhibition zones of 8mm each against both *C. albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* was produced by *Cladosporium herbarum*. The finding of this study is in agreement with a study conducted by [22]. A similar finding was also reported by [23]. A comparably lower inhibition zones of these pathogens by *Aspergillus* spp. was also reported by [26]. Since, the size and position of the growth inhibition zone is a consequence of many dynamic systems, it is doubtful to compare one antibiotic agent against another on the basis of inhibition zone size [27].

Fungal species are potential producers of bioactive compounds [11]. Fungi are known to produce a plethora of natural products. About 47% (33,500 in a total of 70,000 metabolites obtained from microbes) of the bioactive secondary metabolites of microbes sources are from fungi [28].

Table 5 of the present study, displayed the molecular formula and molecular structure of some important compounds found in fungal extracts. The compounds from the GC-MS analysis were identified based on retention time and peak area. The compounds include Phytol, Diethyl phthalate, Pentafluoropropionate, 2-Octanol, Methanamine, and Propylamine. The presence of these compounds have also been reported in previous reports by [11]. In their study titled GC-MS based characterization, antibacterial, antifungal and anti-oncogenic activity of Ethyl acetate extract of

Aspergillus niger strain AK-16 isolated from Rhizospheric soil.

5.0 Conclusion

The results of the screening analysis carried out in this study, have shown that soils of Kotorkoshi and its environs do harbor fungi capable of producing antibiotics against some major human pathogens. This study has demonstrated, that both narrow and broad-spectrum antibiotic producing fungi may be recovered from the soils of Kotorkoshi and its environs in Zamfara state. Microscopic examination and phylogenetic analysis of the isolates revealed them as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Cladosporium herbarum*, and *Epicoccum nigrum*. Furthermore, the GC-MS analysis showed the presence of bioactive compounds such as: Phytol, Diethylphthalate, 2-octanol, Methanamine, Propylamine and Pentafluoropropionate which are known for various pharmaceutical applications.

6.0 Recommendations

Fractionation and NMR should be employed for isolation and purification of these compounds with antibiotic activities produced by these fungi. Further studies should focus on the mechanism of action of isolated bioactive compounds from these microorganisms to broaden the horizon of research in antibiotic drug discovery.

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8.0 References

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